

Costs of invasive non-native species on Scottish heath and moorland

Interview and workshop report

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Introduction

Invasive non-native species (INNS) are species introduced into novel environments via direct (e.g., release of unwanted pets) or indirect (e.g., in contaminated soil) human action, and which go on to have a negative ecological, economic, or societal impact (Mooney, 2001). To date, the majority of research into INNS impacts and costs has focused on agriculture and forestry (Haubrock *et al.*, 2021). However, INNS impacts are felt across landscapes, with potential interactions with climate change, impacts on water availability and flooding, and widespread damages to biodiversity (Roberts and Mitchell, 2024). Typically, INNS research limits itself to only plant and animal invaders and does not incorporate introduced pests and pathogens. This is despite introduced pests and pathogens having significant recorded negative impacts on ecosystems, economy and society (e.g., Ash dieback (Mitchell *et al.*, 2014).

Definitions

Invasive non-native species (INNS): Species introduced into novel environments via direct (e.g., release of unwanted pets) or indirect (e.g., in contaminated soil) human action, and which go on to have a negative ecological, economic, or societal impact. Including invasive non-native pests and pathogens.

Heath and moorland: Upland open areas, dominated by low scrub and excluding forested areas.

Heath and moorland have been recognised as habitats under particular risk from INNS, including due to introduced pests and pathogens (Mitchell, 2022). Despite this risk, a previous literature review established a limited understanding of current impacts of INNS in heath and moorland habitats, but identified a number of potential impacts should a novel INNS be introduced into the moorland and heath environment (Roberts and Mitchell, 2024). Given the importance of these habitats not just for biodiversity, but also flood mitigation, water quality, culture and tourism (Roberts *et al.*, 2023), understanding the potential implications of INNS incursion into heath and moorland could prove important for preserving these services.

Although published data on INNS in heath and moorlands is limited (Roberts and Mitchell, 2024), it is likely that more hands-on action is being taken, but has not been recorded in publicly accessible places. This is supported by the finding of grey-literature on costs of INNS in Scotland missing from an international databases of costs, InvaCost (Roberts and Li, 2023). We therefore carry out interviews and workshops to begin to map and capture this information, and shape future research to formalise the informal data available in practice.

Objectives

Overarching objective: Estimate the potential costs of control of invasive species, which include plant pests and pathogens in vulnerable habitats in Scotland and the economic and social implications of this control.

Specific objectives:

1. Identify any current control of INNS, including pests and pathogens, occurring on heath and moorland not found during search of literature.
2. Identify potential measure of INNS control in heath and moorland.
3. Refine potential impacts of INNS in heath and moorland habitats identified in Roberts and Mitchell (2024).
4. Identify high priority areas for future costing.

Methods

Study selection

A previous literature review identified that the majority of knowledge on INNS impacts and costs within Scotland is within agriculture and forestry, with limited understanding of impacts in vulnerable habitats (Roberts and Li, 2023). A study of plant pests and pathogens further identified heaths and moorlands as areas of high vulnerability (Mitchell, 2022).

Interviews

Interviews were carried out with individuals who have a role in heath and moorland management, and/or INNS control. This includes those with hands-on roles, as well as those in managerial roles with budget/resource allocation experience (Table 1). We did not target individual users of heath and moorland, however representatives of interest groups of users may be relevant where they have knowledge of ecosystems services that may be impacted by INNS. Interviewees were not expected to be representative of INNS or heath and moorland management across Scotland, but to cover the breadth of available knowledge.

Invites were sent to existing contacts of researchers, and groups or organisation identified through internet search. Those contacted were asked to pass on details of the invitation to others they think may be interested. Interviews were considered complete when no new information was available. Interviews were carried out over Webex video conferencing platform, and were recorded for note taking purposes.

Table 1 Stakeholder types invited to interview

Stakeholder type	Reason for invite
Environmental managers (e.g., rangers)	Experience of practical INNS and/or heath and moorland management, therefore able to identify current or potential control measures and impacts of INNS invasion.
Environmental NGOs with areas of heath and moorland	Experience of heath and moorland management, including funding and current or potential INNS control.
INNS control specialists	Experience of practical INNS and/or heath and moorland management, therefore able to identify current or potential control measures and impacts of INNS invasion. Also experience of costs of control.
Governmental organisations with management responsibility over heath and moorland or INNS	Experience of heath and moorland management, including funding and current or potential INNS control.

Workshops

The workshop was carried out with individuals of organisations with direct knowledge of costs of carrying out INNS control on heath and moorlands, and costs of damages incurred because of INNS or other heath and moorland degradation. These individuals had responsibilities for management of specific heath or moorland, or an overarching responsibility for multiple

projects and were identified based on existing contacts of researchers and the preceding interviews.

The workshop included discussions on the participants knowledge of INNS control currently carried out in heath and moorland, the potential options for INNS control, and priorities for future work. Virtual white boards (Miro boards. www.miro.com) were used alongside discussion to capture notes from participants, and votes for priority research areas. The workshop was recorded for note taking purpose.

Results

NOTE: All results presented are the outcomes of the interviews and workshops, and, though representing important expert knowledge, may not be reported in the scientific literature.

Interviews

We carried out eight interviews between 9th August and 6th September 2024 over Webex, with each interview lasting approximately 30 minutes. Interviewees included representatives from NatureScot (overarching INNS experts and individual site managers), Scottish Government, Heather Trust, Joint Nature Conservation Committee (JNCC), Scottish Land and Estates, and Scottish Deer Management Group.

Workshop

One workshop was conducted on 4th February 2025 and lasted two and a half hours. There were eight attendees from: NatureScot, Heather Trust, Peatland Action, Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, and North Harris Trust. Three of the workshop attendees were also involved in the interviews.

Objective One: Existing INNS in heath and moorland

Heath and moorland were overall considered to have low INNS burden by participants, although a number of INNS were identified. It was also noted that “native-invasives” are more often of concern, with bracken and ticks often dominating discussion in both interviews and workshops. Impacts of INNS were expected to be highly location specific, with footpaths and areas linked to riparian sites particularly vulnerable due to higher potential for introduction. Additionally, the open nature of heath and moorland, in comparison to woodlands and agriculture, were suggested to make INNS easier to work around (e.g., livestock can graze in different areas, footpaths can be easily diverted). As a result, higher densities of INNS may be needed before they are considered a problem, in comparison to woodland or agriculture. This higher threshold for INNS to become a “problem” can also lead to it being harder to get buy-in from landowners for control until populations are well established, potentially increasing costs. Additional barriers to management were recognised as challenging, or non-existent, funding for maintaining cleared populations, because funding focuses typically on initial removal. The need for dry weather and specialised contractors was also noted.

Species

Rhododendron

Rhododendron ponticum was the INNS species most often controlled in heath and moorlands, often linked to control being carried out in woodland habitats. As priorities for rhododendron control moves towards landscape scale control heath and moorlands were expected to be included more often, and so control may increase. Although control measures may be similar to that in forestry, seed dispersal was reported to be higher in open habitats, suggesting a need for additional modelling to understand heath and moorland rhododendron populations. Given the open nature of heath and moorlands, drone surveys were identified as a potential useful tool for mapping spread.

Methods of rhododendron control include manual removal and herbicides. While specialised contractors may be needed in some cases, volunteer groups were recognised as an important component of manual removal in accessible areas. Manual removal can involve removal by hand, either through pulling or digging, or mechanical removal such as flailing of plants. Manual removal also requires disposal of remaining plant material to prevent re-sprouting. The preferred method for disposal was reported as burning on site, using a metal sheet to prevent spread. However, burying was reported to be favoured by contractors, where care must be taken to ensure all plant matter is buried deep enough to prevent resprouting. For large plants digging up and flipping to expose the roots is also possible, although this has the disadvantage of shading areas underneath the flipped plants. Herbicidal control of rhododendron can include spraying or targeted application of glyphosate. Spraying is applicable in only a limited number of cases, due to knock on impacts on other vegetation, while a targeted approach reduces risk of impact on surrounding vegetation.

Rhododendron control was also used to reduce the spread of Phytophthora, as one of its main hosts. Although Phytophthora control is normally linked to the protection of woodlands, and its control in heath and moorlands will reduce spread between woodland sites, damage to heather by the pathogen has also been recorded. This is the only pathogen identified by stakeholders within heath and moorland.

Sitka spruce

Picea sitchensis (Sitka spruce) encroachment from forestry, also called “Sitka rain”, was identified by many stakeholders. Sitka escape from forestry was reported at the edge of forest plantations, and expected to spread across heath and moorland if not controlled. Sitka control is generally limited to mechanical removal, although heavy grazing was also suggested. Some use of muir burn to attempt to control Sitka spread has also been reported, although the efficacy was uncertain. Anecdotally Sitka encroachment is typically less of a concern for highly managed sites, where individual seedlings are removed during general operations, but can become out of control on more remote, less visited, sites where seedlings can establish. Sitka encroachment is reduced where water levels are increased as part of peatland restoration, and is funded under peatland action funding. However, this covers only initial removal and not ongoing maintenance.

Sitka spruce control can have the added complication of a felling licence being required for trees once they reach a threshold diameter. Conflicts between woodland expansion and preservation of heath and moorland habitats was also identified as a challenge.

Sika deer

Cervus nippon (Sika deer), currently present within woodland, were identified as a potential species which may spread into heath and moorland. This was particularly linked to woodland expansion, which may lead to a population explosion due to increased resource availability. Control of sika deer through shooting is well established as part of ongoing deer control, although additional resources may be needed to cover wider areas or areas with limited accessibility. Availability of skilled stalkers was identified as a limitation on Sika control. Costs may be offset, however, by sale of venison.

Additional species

Other species were also identified by individual interviewees and discussed at the workshops. Although less widespread these species are having impacts at local levels, with the potential for future spread.

Gunnera manicata (Giant Rhubarb) was reported in the extreme west of Scotland, including Lewis and Harris, with some spread to the mainland west coast. Adapted to mild oceanic climates with little frost, Giant rhubarb has the potential to alter highly specialised west coast habitats, and threaten plant species within them. Control of giant rhubarb is typically carried out via herbicide, however due to proximity to water this can be challenging. Smaller plants may be dug out, but care must be taken with fragile roots. Giant rhubarb regenerates and spreads easily, and has a persistent soil seed bank, meaning that control is often a multi-year process.

Rubus spectabilis (Salmonberry) is a small, low growing species from North America or New Zealand which smothers native species. It is spread by birds, so it is impractical and difficult to eradicate, particularly on migration routes. Control of salmonberry has so far been through mechanical removal and herbicide. The roots are very friable and extensive making removal often challenging.

Acaena novae-zelandiae (Piri-piri burr) has previously been limited in spread, but is now expanding, and reported across Scotland. Piri-piri burr is difficult to eradicate due to being spread by dogs. Participants reported that if the area has a high amount of hikers, visitors, or tourists it will continue to return.

Epilobium brunnescens (New Zealand willowherb) was reported widely, but its impacts on native species are so far unknown. *Erinus alpinus* (Fairy foxglove) is garden escapee, not yet widespread but thought to outcompete natives. This species was identified as one where education on careful planting would be beneficial. Invasive mosses have also been recorded on access tracks and bare peat.

Azaela species, *Lysichiton americanus* (skunk cabbage), *Impatiens glandulifera* (Himalayan balsam), and *Reynoutria japonica* (Japanese knotweed) are more often found in riparian

habitats, but some incursion into heath and moorland has been recorded, and control has followed the removal and herbicide methods developed for control in riparian habitats

Social impacts

Understanding of INNS in heath and moorland by visitors was anticipated to be low, with most species not being readily identifiable as either positive or negative. The main exception to this was reported to be Rhododendron. This was anticipated because as an ornamental Rhododendron is readily recognised, and the dense foliage and bright flowers can be considered to be attractive. Conversely, removal of Rhododendron creates apparently barren, bare landscapes, at least in the short term. Additionally, otters and badgers can use Rhododendron as resting spaces, leading to further opposition to removal. Careful consideration of removal can reduce these negative impacts, and anecdotally large stands of Rhododendron can cause navigational difficulty for hillwalkers.

Similar to removal of Rhododendron, removal of mature Sitka spruce may alter the landscape, suggested to impact the visual value. Species using the Sitka, including red squirrels, pine martens and reptiles may also be highly valued, and present additional social opposition to removal.

Control by both burning and herbicides are reported as often politically and socially contentious. Large scale burning can impact access for recreation, and air quality can be reduced. Burning is perceived to release carbon, even where alternatives, such as burying for Rhododendron, may have larger impacts. Herbicides in addition to poor social image were suggested to have the potential to cause downstream impacts on fisheries. Hunting of deer, and the sale of venison from Sika deer, can increase the social acceptability of control, however, anti-hunting lobbies can cause social opposition.

Interactions with other threats to heath and moorland were suggested to increase potential social impacts. Potentially invasive grasses and Sitka spruce are expected to burn well, and declines in vegetation to lead to drying of peat and higher fire risk. The impacts of climate change, particularly related to water flow rate, were expected to be worsened.

Costs

Full eradication was generally considered cost prohibitive for species that are already well established across interview and workshop participants. Across species, higher costs of control would be expected for:

- Areas that are less accessible – this may be due to elevation, distance from access tracks, or water levels.
- Low densities of individuals – although total costs may be lower for smaller populations or lower densities, this increases the cost per individual due to increased searching time.
- Well established populations – control will be easier early into invasion, where areas are typically smaller, and for plant species individuals also physically smaller and easier to remove.

For specific costs of identified INNS in heath and moorland see Table 2.

Table 2 Costs of control of INNS in heath and moorlands, including potential reasons for higher or lower estimates.

Species	Lower estimate	Higher estimate	Additional considerations	References
Sika deer	<p>£35/deer (payment for additional costs above basic cost).</p> <p>Supplemented through income from game shooting and market for venison.</p> <p>Deer removed as part of general deer population management.</p>	<p>£185/deer</p> <p>Availability of skilled stalkers increases costs, or alters where and when deer can be taken, which may not be the most cost-efficient option otherwise.</p>	<p>Fencing may be needed to protect vulnerable areas, as complete eradication is not possible.</p> <p>Costs of Sika deer control are tied to control of native species, and it is probably not useful to focus on Sika deer alone.</p>	(NatureScot, 2024) and workshop
Giant rhubarb	£1/ha (over total area, not only infested area).	<p>Unknown (likely similar to rhododendron).</p> <p>Chemical control close to water will require more highly specialised removal.</p> <p>Presence of plants on neighbouring sites.</p>	Giant rhubarb seeds survive for 10-15 years in seed banks, meaning long monitoring period required.	Workshop
Salmonberry	Unknown.	Unknown.	<p><i>Rubus fruticosus</i> closest relative and may provide approximate costs.</p> <p>Control complicated by spread by birds, making reinvasion almost certain.</p> <p>Very fragile root system, complete removal will be challenging.</p>	Workshop

Fairy foxglove	Unknown.	Unknown. As an ornamental garden plant reinvasion likely close to residential areas.	As a small herbaceous plant removal may not be possible without causing more damage to the ecosystem.	Workshop
Piri-piri burr	Unknown.	Unknown.	Spread by dogs and hillwalkers, so reinvasion highly likely.	Workshop
Sitka spruce	£500/ha Optimum density of seedlings. Can be carried out as part of other running of estate (e.g., during native tree planting).	£3,000/ha (£6,000/ha if including bog restoration) Once over certain diameter felling licence required. Waterlogged areas and challenges of accessibility. Protected species may prevent removal – red squirrel, pine marten, reptiles.	Re-establishment highly likely due to continued seed encroachment. Will not establish on a healthy peat bog. Peatland Action will fund initial removal, but not ongoing maintenance.	(Glenk <i>et al.</i> , 2021) and workshop
Rhododendron	£50/ha Accessible areas cleared by volunteer groups.	£5,600/ha Used by otter and badgers. Reinvasion from ornamentals likely. Close to water safe glyphosate is	Potential for higher seed dispersal in open areas than seen in woodlands.	(Jackson, 2008) and workshop

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Objective Two: Potential new INNS in heath and moorland

In general control of INNS in heath and moorlands was expected to rely on similar techniques to those applied in forestry and woodlands. For many current large-scale eradication programs some element of open ground would be included, and so methods were reported to be adapted as a matter of course. One potentially challenging element introduced in heath and moorland may be the terrain, particularly in wet areas, and access to bogs for manual removal was identified to potentially require boats or specialised machinery. Training both on the benefits of forestry methods for INNS control, and on the practicality of carrying them out, were also recognised as important.

Direct pest and pathogen control was not widely considered by any participant, although fungi were discussed at the workshop as a potential INNS, which would cause devastating impacts, particularly if impacting heather. Small scale outbreaks of fungi in *Vaccinium* sp. were reported by one workshop attendee. Chronic wasting disease in deer was also identified as a possible pathogen INNS which may already be present in Scotland.

Some analogue was suggested with heather beetle, a native beetle that can cause large scale heather decline. Heather beetle was reported to have been previously controlled by parasitoid wasps, with outbreaks in high numbers occurring as early as the 1970s. Control was particularly challenging because outbreaks are often sporadic, and so hard to predict. The only management of heather beetle suggested by stakeholders in interviews was burning of heather, although not all stakeholders were certain as to whether this was indeed best practise. In addition to removing the heather beetle itself heather was reported to recover stronger after first burns, and so may be more resilient to INNS incursion in the future, although this is only anecdotal. In the workshops stakeholders further elaborated that a holistic approach to management has also proven to be beneficial in heather beetle management. Because outbreaks of heather beetle are so challenging to predict, the best defence was often the maintenance of healthy plants. Beetles were reported to attack weaker plants more readily, and so a healthy system will be more robust against invasion. Climate change is also a key factor in heather beetle emergence, and systems that are more resilient to climate change will therefore stand a better chance of resisting invasion.

Although ticks are not an INNS within heath and moorlands, and do not cause damage to the habitat per se, they do harbour pathogens harmful to humans, livestock and gamebirds and were identified by participants in the same context as INNS. The potential to become hosts of non-native pathogens was also identified. Although not currently monitored outside of domestic and game bird species, potential pathogens in mammal populations are also possible. For the control of ticks increased regularity of dipping of sheep, alternative tick vectors, has been carried out by participant organisations. Direct dosing of grouse against ticks is also conducted by some shooting estates, to protect chicks.

Overall, the most likely defence against pests and pathogens, as well as more traditional INNS, was thought to be maintaining a healthy, resilient and diverse ecosystem. Diversity here relating

not just to inter-species diversity, but intra-species diversity, where variation between individuals may mean that some individuals have higher resistance than others to novel pests and pathogens. Integrated pest management, a holistic approach carried out in agriculture for the control of pests with reduced reliance on chemicals, was suggested as one method on which to base pest and pathogen control in heath and moorlands. All other pest and pathogen control options, including insecticides or fungicides, were anticipated to be too challenging to apply in heath and moorland habitats. Insecticides would have significant impacts on native fauna and so be unacceptable for use. Fungal controls which contain copper would have damaging impacts on mollusc species.

Given the overall limited potential to control new INNS, and particularly pests and pathogens, within heath and moorlands, the importance of prevention of entry and surveillance was highlighted. Escapees from ornamental gardens, for which there are limited controls compared to those in place for forestry, were highlighted as a potential space for increased attention, as well as the need to prevent spread during removal or restoration work. The large areas and low human presence across heath and moorlands, coupled with the potentially cryptic nature of new INNS, can make surveillance challenging. Citizen science is also more complex than in more densely used areas, however, training of expert observers may be a possibility, particularly where monitoring can overlap with other outdoor activities.

Objective Three: Impacts of INNS in heath and moorland

Impacts of INNS on heath and moorland will depend highly on density, although one interviewee did identify that the open nature of heath and moorland could lead to INNS going unnoticed or ignored until they are well established, causing a larger problem for removal.

The most often recognised impact was that of contributions to climate change, particularly due to drying out of peat soils leading to release of carbon. Impacts on ability to mitigate impacts of climate change were also highlighted as being of high importance, particularly related to water flow rate regulation, which can mitigate both drought and flood events, but may be reduced due to increased woody vegetation cover.

The typically wet nature of heath and moorland means that downstream effects of INNS were also highlighted as a concern. This includes spread of INNS downstream into productive areas, as well as spread of the impacts of INNS. Sitka spruce was particularly highlighted as potentially impacting fisheries due to potential for increasing the acidity of run-off.

Tourism was identified as potentially being impacted by burning, as has been reported in Ilkley moor in England. Removal of rhododendron can be controversial as it can be preferred due to its bright flowers, and the immediate aftermath of removal is not visually pleasing. The homogenisation of habitats due to INNS encroachment will also lead to reduced variation in habitats, and the loss of iconic Scottish landscapes.

Impacts on game birds were identified particularly in relation to ticks, however any introduced pest or pathogen which impacts game birds would be expected to cause damage to the industry.

Objective Four: Important costing gaps

Priorities for costing gaps were most often focused around impacts on biodiversity and climate change, including benefits arising from protection as well as costs. Comparisons were made to forestry, particularly to be able to compare costs of preserving carbon and biodiversity in heath and moorland. The importance of cultural connection was also highlighted, including the importance of including current land users in decision making, and ensuring their value of the land is included. Given the current unknown nature of INNS in heath and moorland we were not able to rank costing gaps, but have grouped them within Table 3.

Table 3 Priority costing gaps for INNS in heath and moorland

Gap	Reasons for prioritisation provided by participants
Costs associated with carbon losses	<p>Vegetation and soil loss in heath and moorland through INNS will lead to loss of carbon in both soil and vegetation. Understanding the magnitude of impact, and how this compares to similar losses in forestry, was highlighted as important for Scotland's climate change goals. This was particularly important in light of the importance of peat soils to Scotland's greenhouse gas emissions targets, and the funding associated with peatland restoration.</p> <p>The feedback loop between climate change increasing the likelihood of INNS invasion, and INNS having the potential to increase climate change through accelerating carbon losses, was also identified as of high priority to consider.</p>
Costs associated with biodiversity losses	Costs that were associated with biodiversity losses as a result of INNS were outlined as a loss of ecosystem resilience and a loss of ecosystems services provided by native biodiversity. As with climate change this was particularly mentioned in relation to comparisons with forestry.
Costs associated with water quality or flow rate	Costs related to water flow and quality were linked to impacts on food and drink industry, particularly the whiskey industry, impacts on fishing and the additional risks of drought and flooding. Soil erosion, and links to climate as well as ecosystem decline, were identified as important associated costs with water flow rate.
Cost efficiencies due to new technology	<p>New technology, such as drones and AI, which may be used to control INNS more efficiently were identified as potential sites for costs savings.</p> <p>Drone technology can be linked to AI to map the spread of INNS plant species and potentially manage species through targeted spraying and by mapping the extent of spread on moorland using LiDAR and multi-spectral imaging at a large scale. This was linked to national level decision making around management funding, including landscape level decisions to maintain diverse Scottish landscapes. Lightweight swarm-robots could aid in managing INNS in difficult to access landscapes.</p>

	<p>Various types of genetic technological advances were discussed such as INNS detection through eDNA and the possibilities around using CRISPR, but there needs to a consideration of ethics and risks.</p> <p>There was some scepticism over the use of AI and drones, with questions being asked about how good drones can be to pick up on invasive species, and whether drones plus AI can pick up on bracken and treat them using spraying technology, something which is currently not permitted.</p>
Spatial differences in costs of management	Data on spatial differences in costs were identified as important for prioritisation of funding. This would need to factor into any available support for control.
Costs and benefits to cultural practice	<p>Potential cultural impacts were identified as grazing and game shooting declines due to loss of vegetation. Impacts on recreational fishing as a result of water quality declines were also highlighted.</p> <p>On the other hand, cultural practise can be incorporated into INNS control. Conservative grazing can be utilised to trample down younger INNS plants, and cultural knowledge and smart breed selection is important for success. A stronger market for venison can result in deer management being more economical. More management of those landscapes should result in more monitoring by gamekeepers to aid the understanding of INNS presence, and there are benefits of INNS control in terms of green jobs.</p> <p>It was also noted by one workshop participant that at a time when Gaelic indigenous practices and culture are highly endangered, any form of environment management done without indigenous input may further the decline of Gaels as a people in the Highlands and Islands. This perspective needs to be considered and looked at with respect and care.</p>
Citizen science	Citizen science and the role it can play in monitoring and reporting INNS can serve to help the public understand the threats of inadvertently releasing invasive species such as rhododendrons. There has been evidence of this working in tree pest and disease reporting.
Funding models	Long-term efficiency was highlighted as important, linked to long-term funding. Instead of relying too much on short-term funding (year to year), when INNS control requires multi-year, steady control. Therefore, money spent could be wasted without continuity. Long-term efficiency is also affected by relying on land managers to keep applying for the short-term grants.

Discussion

Although our interviews and workshops do back up the findings from previous literature reviews that control of invasive non-native species on heath and moorland is less common than forestry or agriculture, we do identify control of species that were not reported in the literature. Sitka spruce in particular was identified by all interviewees and discussed at length within the workshop, but is not reported elsewhere. Additional species identified include: Sika deer, Fairy Foxglove, Salmonberry, Piri-Piri burr, and Giant Rhubarb. No control of INNS in the form of pests and pathogens was reported by any stakeholders. Understanding of costs were limited, although some ranges were identified for the more abundant species.

That the literature on INNS in heath and moorland does not fully reflect the extent of INNS control being carried out may have potential implications for management plans, funding, and identification of priorities for management, if this control is not considered. This may have particular implications for peatland management, and long-term carbon storage, if the threat of INNS is overlooked.

Priorities for costing varied between stakeholders and likely reflects the currently unknown and disjointed nature of INNS control in heath and moorland. Interactions with climate change was the most consistently mentioned priority and garnered much discussion within the workshop. Understanding how INNS threats are increased with a changing climate will be important for forecasting future management of heath and moorlands and predicting potential future costs. The potential for INNS to worsen the impacts of climate change through causing catastrophic decline in vegetation should also be considered.

Although native, across interviews and workshops bracken was identified as of high priority for control as a “native invasive”. Increasing bracken populations in recent years were reported to be linked to declines in grazing area, increased difficulties in access, and decreased water flow. Bracken was recognised to cut across human and animal health due to hosting of ticks and its toxic nature, in addition to its impact on biodiversity and landscapes. This leads to a consideration of native versus non-native and the blurring of boundaries around several native species that cause problems for conservation.

Conclusion and next steps

Invasive non-native species are not a major current concern within heath and moorlands. However, a number of species are being controlled, and potential impacts are recognised, with the potential for these to increase in coming years. Better understanding of the potential invaders, and the impacts they may have, will therefore be important for future management in heath and moorlands.

The next steps in this project will be to focus on specific case studies to begin to fill in some of the high priority gaps, and identify data needs. For further information or to be involved in future case studies please email: Michaela.roberts@hutton.ac.uk

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